

Development of porous carbons from urea formaldehyde resin for carbon dioxide adsorption

Deepak Tiwari, Haripada Bhunia* and Pramod K. Bajpai

Department of Chemical Engineering, Thapar Institute of Engineering & Technology (Deemed to be University), Patiala-147 004, Punjab, India

E-mail : deepak.tiwari@thapar.edu, hbhunia@thapar.edu, pramod.iitk77@gmail.com

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Abstract : Nitrogen enrichment considered to be effective in improving adsorption capacity, adsorbate-adsorbent interaction and regenerability. In this work, by using nanocasting technique, mesoporous zeolite as template and urea-formaldehyde resin as precursor, we have successfully prepared nitrogen enriched porous carbons. Several sophisticated characterization techniques were used for thorough characterization of adsorbents. CO₂ adsorption capacity of the adsorbents under dynamic conditions was evaluated thermogravimetrically and CO₂ uptake of 1.24 mmol g⁻¹ at 700°C with complete regenerability over four multiple adsorption-desorption cycle was observed. Fractional order kinetic model completely described CO₂ adsorption on prepared carbons. From the thermodynamic evaluation, this adsorption process is found to be spontaneous, feasible and exothermic in nature. Heterogeneous surface of adsorbent was confirmed by best fitting Freundlich isotherm.

Keywords : Nanocasting, urea-formaldehyde, kinetics, isotherm, regeneration.

I. Introduction

CO₂, a major greenhouse gas is the paramount contributor for the global warming. Its concentration increased in the atmosphere up to a level of 408.53 ppm (2018) due to burning of fossil fuels^{1,2}. It is expected that if no major actions are taken, it's concentration may increase upto a level of 550 ppm by 2100³. Therefore, various methods have been developed in order to reduce its concentration and among them carbon dioxide capture and sequestration (CCS) system has found to have potential to reduce its concentration⁴⁻⁷.

Among the available CCS technologies, adsorption using porous solid adsorbents was found to be more effective because of high CO₂ uptake capacity and low energy consumption. On a large scale, amine absorption has been used but due to several disadvantage like high cost, corrosion and several other problems it was not used maximum⁸. Also, apart from high adsorption capacity, they are trying to

improve their selectivity and regenerability by using amine modification but face problems like blocking of pores and poor stability. Therefore, use of carbon based adsorbents is another approach found to be effective which is developed in this work by using nanocasting technique. Here, nanocasting technique is preferred as compared to other techniques like carbonization and activation of carbon containing precursor, sol gel process⁹ because by using this technique it is possible to control pore characteristics. CO₂ adsorption capacity and selectivity towards adsorbent was also enhanced by using incorporation of heteroatoms in carbon-matrix¹⁰.

N-rich carbons developed by Drage *et al.*¹¹ from urea-formaldehyde and melamine-formaldehyde resins, at 25°C under 100% CO₂ flow exhibited CO₂ uptake of 1.86 and 1.03 mmol g⁻¹.

Various researchers tried to develop adsorbents either by physical/chemical activation or by direct carbonization and evaluated their uptake capacity for

static conditions mainly at 25°C which resulted to be disadvantage for their studies. It was reported that direct carbonization was time consuming and required excess amount of energy. To overcome this gap, nanocasting technique was employed for adsorbent development which enhanced the textural properties of the adsorbent. Performance of adsorbent was evaluated under dynamic conditions at 100% CO₂ concentrations and at variable temperatures (30–100°C). Kinetics, adsorption isotherm, thermodynamics and energy calculations studies have also been conducted in this study.

II. Materials and methods

A. Materials

All the chemicals used are of AR grade and were purchased from M/s S. D. Fine Chem. Limited. Dry N₂ and CO₂ of 99.999% were supplied by M/s. Sigma Gases Services, India

B. Synthesis of N-enriched nanostructured carbon adsorbent

Typically, urea formaldehyde resin was mixed with mesoporous zeolite until a homogenous solution appears, followed by curing for 3 h. After this, carbonization-activation were carried out at carbonization temperature (700°C) and in the last template removal were carried out by dissolution of obtained carbonized sample in NaOH solution followed by filtration. Also, at the same condition, direct carbonized sample was prepared which was considered as a reference sample.

C. Characterization of adsorbent

The synthesized adsorbents have been characterized for their elemental (CHNS) using Thermo-Scientific Flash 2000 organic elemental analyzer, textural property using N₂ sorption isotherms at 77 K on a Micromeritics ASAP 2010 sorption analyzer, Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method, and Barrett-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) model. SEM using JEOL JSM-6510 LV scanning electron microscope and TEM using Philips CM-200 for surface morphology were carried out.

D. CO₂ adsorption measurement

Adsorption experiments were carried out by using TGA Q500, USA instruments. Here 20 mg of samples were placed in platinum pan, followed by pretreatment for 2 h to remove moisture or any another adsorbed gases. After completion of 2 h, temperature was cooled to desired adsorption temperature i.e. (30–100°C) which was performed under CO₂ atmosphere. Desorption study was carried out after the sample saturated at 200°C under N₂ atmosphere for 2 h.

E. Adsorption kinetic models

To determine the controlling mechanism of adsorption processes such as mass transfer and chemical reaction, the pseudo-first order, pseudo-second order equation and the fractional order rate applied.

The pseudo-first order rate equation is given as¹² :

$$q_t - q_e (1 - \exp(-k_f t)) \quad (1)$$

Pseudo-second order model¹² :

$$q_t = \frac{k_2 q_e^2 t}{1 + k_2 q_e t} \quad (2)$$

The fractional order model is :

$$q_t = q_e - \frac{1}{[(n-1)k_n/m]t^n + (1/q_e^{n-1})]^{1/n-1}} \quad (3)$$

where, q_e : amount adsorbed at equilibrium in mmol g⁻¹, q_t : amount adsorbed at time t in a min, k_1 : rate constant of pseudo-first order in min⁻¹, k_2 : rate constant of pseudo-second order in g mmol⁻¹ min⁻¹.

Sufficiency of each model is ascertained by error function evaluation :

Error (%) =

$$\sqrt{\frac{\sum [(q_{t(\text{exp})} - q_{t(\text{pred})})/q_{t(\text{exp})}]^2}{N-1}} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

where, $q_{t(\text{exp})}$: experimental CO₂ loading, $q_{t(\text{pred})}$: predicted CO₂ loading.

F. Adsorption isotherm models

Adsorption isotherms are mathematical models

used to explain the distribution of adsorbate molecules among adsorbent. For predicting the adsorption capacity, surface properties and affinity of the adsorbent, we have used two commonly used models that are important to analyze the equilibrium experimental data i.e. Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms and Temkin.

Langmuir isotherm model¹³ :

$$q_t = \frac{q_m K_L P}{1 + K_L P} \quad (5)$$

Freundlich isotherm model :

$$q_e = K_F P^{1/n} \quad (6)$$

Temkin isotherm model :

$$q_e = B \ln(K_T P) \quad (7)$$

where, q_m : maximum adsorption capacity in mmol g^{-1} , P : CO_2 partial pressure in atm, K_L : Langmuir constant in atm^{-1} , K_F and n : Freundlich.

G. Adsorption thermodynamics

Thermodynamic properties for CO_2 adsorption process in terms of Gibbs free energy change (ΔG°), enthalpy change (ΔH°), and entropy change (ΔS°), can be represented as¹⁵ :

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln(K_{eq}) \quad (8)$$

$$\ln(K_{eq}) = -\frac{\Delta H^\circ}{R} \frac{1}{T} + \frac{\Delta S^\circ}{R} \quad (9)$$

K_{eq} : equilibrium constant for adsorption¹⁵.

III. Results and discussion

A. Characterization of adsorbents

Specific surface area, pore volume and PSD data

N_2 adsorption-desorption of the sample (Fig. 1) shows Type IV isotherm having a hysteresis H3 loop. Nanocasting technique helps in existence of mesoporosity in samples. Sample shows surface area ($337.10 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) and pore volume ($0.65 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$). Also, a small micropore volume of $0.08 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$ was seen in the sample. It was seen that sample prepared at same carbonization temperature shows dif-

Fig. 1. N_2 adsorption-desorption isotherms at -196°C of samples.

ferent nitrogen adsorption like sample prepared by nanocasting technique show higher nitrogen adsorption whereas sample prepared by direct carbonization has almost negligible amount of nitrogen adsorption and non-porous in nature.

Elemental content

Nanocasted sample shows 56.35% C, 26.27% N and 17% O while the sample prepared by direct carbonization shows 63% C, 22% N and 10% O. It was observed that the direct carbonization sample shows lesser content of oxygen and nitrogen. This shows that the effect of the template on the composition of materials.

SEM analysis

From the SEM image [Fig. 2(a and b)], it was clearly observed that the direct carbonization sample was completely non-porous and the effect of nanocasting in the development of adsorbent from completely nonporous to a well developed porous structure is obtained. This observation is in agreement with N_2 adsorption-desorption isotherm.

Fig. 2. SEM images of (a) nanocasted sample and (b) direct carbonized sample.

Fig. 3. TEM images of (a) nanocasted sample and (b) direct carbonized sample.

TEM analysis

From the TEM micrographs [Fig. 3(a and b)], effect of template in development of the sample in the nanostructured range was clearly observed as compare to direct carbonization which shows larger structures.

B. Dynamic CO₂ adsorption-desorption studies

Adsorbent shows higher uptake capacity of 1.24 mmol g⁻¹ (Fig. 4) which could be because of higher porous nature and nitrogen content as confirmed from SEM, TEM and CHN analysis. On the other hand sample prepared by direct carbonization which is because of non-porous nature, lesser content of nitrogen and oxygen etc. Also, decrease in CO₂ uptake by increasing the adsorption temperature (Table 1) indicates its exothermic nature.

Fig. 4. CO₂ uptake of prepared carbons at 30°C under pure CO₂ flow.

Table 1. CO₂ uptake (mmol g⁻¹) of nanocasted sample under pure CO₂ at different temperatures

CO ₂ Concentration (%)	Temperature (°C)			
	30	50	75	100
100	1.24	1	0.62	0.55

Fig. 5. Multiple adsorption-desorption curves of nanocasted sample; adsorption at 30°C and desorption at 200°C.

Multiple cycle adsorption experiments with CO₂/N₂ at 30°C

The sample was also tested for 4 different cycles at 100% CO₂ concentration and at 30°C and observed that the sample shows complete regenerability over four different cycles. Same CO₂ uptake capacity was observed.

Fig. 6. CO₂ uptake kinetics at 30°C under pure CO₂ flow.

Adsorption kinetics, isotherm study and thermodynamic study

In the present study, three kinetic models were performed. Fig. 6 shows experimental and predicted data for both the samples. Pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order either overestimated or underestimated in different regions. Fractional order kinetic model provided the best fit as experimental q_e value is in good agreement with the predicted q_e value. This all observations are also confirmed by error% and R^2 value in Table 2.

Table 2. CO₂ uptake kinetic parameters at 30°C under pure CO₂ of prepared carbons

Model	Parameters	Sample	
		Nanocasted	Direct carbonized
Pseudo-first order	k_1	1.49	1.13
	q_e	1.28	0.67
	R^2	0.97	0.98
	Error %	4.29	3.44
Pseudo-second order	k_2	1.99	2.9
	q_e	1.32	0.65
	R^2	0.97	0.95
	Error %	4.6	7.80
Fractional order	k_n	3.28	3.9
	q_e	1.24	0.6
	n	3.59	1.65
	m	2.7	1.2
	R^2	0.99	0.99
	Error %	1.05	2.1

Table 3. Adsorption isotherms of CO₂ adsorption on nanocasted sample

Models	Parameters	Temperature (°C)
Langmuir	q_m	30
	K_L	1.37
	R^2	7.18
Freundlich	K_F	0.94
	n	1.29
	R^2	3.03
Temkin	K_T	0.999
	b	92.83
	R^2	9.33
	R^2	0.97
	R^2	0.999

Also, the isotherm study on the prepared adsorbent was carried out (Table 3) and found Freundlich isotherms fitted well (higher value of R^2) with the experimental results showing heterogeneous nature of the adsorbent surface. Also, exothermic nature is confirmed from the negative value of ΔH° (Table 4). ΔG° value was found to be negative at all temperatures showing spontaneity and feasibility of the adsorption process.

Table 4. Thermodynamic parameters of CO₂ adsorption

Temperature (°C)	ΔG° (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH° (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS° (kJ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)
30	-11.50	-4.75	0.0026
50	-11.01		
75	-12.70		
100	-12.60		

IV. Conclusions

Nanostructured, high porous adsorbent was successfully developed by nanocasting technique, using low cost N-containing precursor and zeolite template and compared with direct carbonization sample. Sample prepared by 700°C shows higher CO₂ uptake capacity with complete regenerability as compared to direct carbonization sample. Furthermore, fractional order kinetic model provided best fit amongst all kinetic models tested. Heterogeneous nature was confirmed from best fit from Freundlich isotherm models. Exothermic nature, feasibility and spontaneity of the process is confirmed from thermodynamic evaluation. Overall, these materials can be used for CO₂ capture from power plant flue gas.

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